

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 101004730

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Ripple Mitigation for slow Extraction Beam Quality Improvement

DELIVERABLE: D5.3

Document identifier:	IFAST-D5.3
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 46 (February 2025)
Report release date:	14/03/2025
Work package:	WP5.3: IFAST-REX
Lead beneficiary:	GSI
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

IFAST-REX concerns the study of beam extraction dynamics with the main goal of applying practical technical mitigations of beam current fluctuations on the 10 μ s to 10 ms time scale for a slowly extracted beam from a synchrotron, also referred to as spill micro-structure. Depending on the slow extraction mechanism, the dominant fluctuations are either caused by ripples of power supply currents for quadrupole magnets, causing a variation of the tune or by the excitation signal for utilized in transverse knock-out extraction. Within IFAST-REX, intensive beam-dynamics studies were performed to minimise the beam response and evaluate robust parameters to smoothen the extracted beam current. Experimental verifications at various facilities provide significant insight into the corresponding accelerator-physics.

The engineering design for two innovative technical systems was performed as a second task. The first device concerns the measurement of the magnet power supply ripples ΔI_{AC} in the presence of a strong DC current I_{DC} . A resolution of $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{DC} < 10^{-6}$ is reached within a bandwidth of 10 Hz to 40 kHz. The second topic contains the low-level control electronics and power amplification chain for the knock-out extraction, providing a power of 500 W within a bandwidth from 0.1 to 20 MHz. For the control, the versatile Software Defined Radio technology is now used on an operational basis and provides multi-band excitations and online feedback; TRL 7 is reached.

The project goal concerning the micro-structure improvement of slow extraction was achieved by the IFAST-REX partners' common effort, as documented in this report.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004730. IFAST began in May 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	Peter Forck and Rahul Singh on behalf of the IFAST-REX consortium Contributions by consortium members: Pablo Arrutia Sota Matthias Barthel Thomas Bass Miguel Cerqueira Bastos Elena Benedetto Tobias Blumenstein Cristopher Cortés García Laurent Dupuy Eike Feldmeier Matthew Fraser Florian Kühtheubl Alessio Mereghetti Philipp Niedermayer Michelangelo Pari Andreas Peters Dale Prokopovich Marco Pullia Claus Schmitzer Stefan Sorge Andrzej Stafiniak Frank Stulle Rebecca Taylor Francesco Velotti Jiangyan Yang	GSI CERN Barthel HF Technik CERN CERN SEEIIST & Tera-Care MIT (only initial phase) HIT & GSI Bergoz™ Instrumentation HIT CERN MedAustron CNAO GSI CERN HIT MedAustron CNAO MedAustron GSI GSI Bergoz™ Instrumentation SEEIIST & CERN CERN GSI	10/03/2025
Reviewed by	M. Vretenar [on behalf of Steering Committee]	CERN	14/03/2025
Approved by	Steering Committee		14/03/2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	TASK DEFINITION AND STRATEGY	5
2	FACILITY STATUS IN YEAR 2021 AT BEGINNING OF IFAST-REX	8
3	HIGH DYNAMIC RANGE CURRENT MEASUREMENT SYSTEM.....	11
3.1	AIM AND GENERAL LAYOUT.....	11
3.2	PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT	12
3.3	FINAL PROTOTYPE	14
3.4	MEASUREMENT RESULTS.....	14
3.5	CONCLUSION FOR HIGH DYNAMIC RANGE CURRENT MEASUREMENT SYSTEM.....	17
4	RF SIGNAL GENERATION FOR KNOCK-OUT EXTRACTION.....	19
4.1	GENERAL PROPERTIES FOR KNOCK-OUT SIGNAL GENERATION	19
4.2	RF CONTROL TECHNICAL SOLUTION EXAMPLE.....	20
4.3	RF SIGNAL OPTIMISATION BY BEAM-BASED MEASUREMENTS	22
4.3.1	<i>Knock-Out Micro-Structure Optimisation at COSY, GSI and HIT.....</i>	<i>22</i>
4.3.2	<i>Knock-Out macro-structure Feedback System</i>	<i>23</i>
4.3.3	<i>Knock-Out Direct Digital Synthesis at HIT.....</i>	<i>25</i>
4.4	RF AMPLIFIER DESIGN	26
4.5	CONCLUSION CONCERNING RF-CONTROL AND AMPLIFIER.....	29
5	BEAM DYNAMICS ACHIEVEMENTS AND EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATIONS	31
5.1	BEAM DYNAMICS FOR KNOCK-OUT MICRO-STRUCTURE IMPROVEMENTS.....	31
5.2	FURTHER STUDIES ON MICRO-STRUCTURE IMPROVEMENTS.....	33
6	DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS	35
7	CONCLUSION	36
8	REFERENCES.....	37

Executive summary

Resonant slow extraction from a synchrotron is exclusively used at all ion medical facilities and for fix-target experiments at CERN and GSI. The beam extraction is performed by creating a 3rd order, non-linear resonance condition and increasing horizontal betatron oscillations. The extracted particles are referred to as spills. Even slight tune variations, caused by current variations for the quadrupole magnets, led to a burst-type extraction of the beam particles, forming temporal micro-structure in the spill. IFAST-REX aims to improve those beam current fluctuations by applying appropriate mitigation schemes (REX stands for Resonance slow EXtraction).

This report focuses on the technical design of novel hardware: Firstly, an extremely high dynamic range measurement of the magnet current fluctuations was realized. Secondly, an optimized realization of the beam excitation components for the knock-out extraction was commissioned. Both technical devices serve as the deliverable for IFAST-REX and could be finalized within the project duration. The Technical Readiness Level 7 is reached.

Magnet current measurement: The determination of the magnet current fluctuations concerns the AC part with a bandwidth from 10 Hz to 40 kHz, as the high-quality switching mode of typical power supplies covers this frequency range. The measurement system comprises two current transformers: An AC transformer covers the entire bandwidth of the AC current I_{AC} with a sensitivity of $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{AC} = 5 \times 10^{-5}$ to be able to monitor fluctuations. To prevent the saturation of the AC transformer, compensation for the DC current is required. For this purpose, a DC current measurement transformer comprises a split-core transformer core and a Hall probe. An extremely sensitive AC current resolution of $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{DC} < 10^{-6}$ with respect to the DC current $I_{DC} \leq 5$ kA was demonstrated.

Knock-out extraction simulation and experimental verification: Besides the variation of the magnet current, the signal spectrum of the transverse knock-out excitation significantly influences the spill micro-structure. This is caused by the diffusion of the particles toward the unstable area and the excitation strength during the particles' movement in the unstable region. Detailed experiments were conducted at the IFAST-REX facilities to investigate the dependences. Based on beam dynamics simulations, it is verified that excitation at multiple bands of the betatron frequency is beneficial. Further measures to improve the beam's robustness to power supply fluctuations are addressed.

Knock-out extraction hardware: To control the low-level RF input signal, an innovative solution was realized, comprising commercial hardware (known as Software Defined Radio) operated by a widely used freeware GNU Radio. To enable multi-band operation, the amplifier's bandwidth covers a large frequency span from 0.1 to 20 MHz with an output power of 500 W. Moreover, the amplifier can be operated with an arbitrary load impedance.

The spill micro-structure was significantly improved based on detailed dynamics considerations and related beam-based verifications performed at several facilities. The development of novel hardware and the usage of dedicated software led to a significant improvement of the spill micro-structure, which can, in principle, be applied at the IFAST-REX facilities. The original project goal was reached thanks to the common efforts of the consortium members.

1 Task Definition and Strategy

Slow extraction from a synchrotron is used at all medical ion therapy centres in Europe and is the primary delivery type for fixed-target experiments at GSI and FAIR. At CERN, demands are increasing for slow extracted beam from PS and SPS for physics experiments and test-beam users. Other accelerator centres in America and Asia, such as BNL, Fermilab and J-PARC, also use slow extraction. The basic procedure of slow extraction consists of exciting a 3rd order resonance created by sextupole fields and a slow, typically several seconds duration extraction by feeding the beam particles into this resonance. Two methods are frequently realised in most accelerator facilities: In the first method, referred to as tune scan, the transverse emittance growth is performed by driving the machine tune towards the 3rd order resonance by means of tune scan realised by a current variation of a quadrupole magnet. While in the second method, the transverse emittance expansion is driven by an external RF field with frequency components correlated with the beam spectra. The resulting diffusion process drives the particles towards the unstable phase space, and this method is referred to as the knock-out extraction method. A third, less frequently used method is empty-bucket channelling. This method is based on a scan of a slightly detuned bunching frequency compared to the revolution frequency. The frequency scan accelerates a subset of particles. Via chromatic tune shift, the resonance condition for extraction is reached for the subset. Further on, RF place displacement is demonstrated at PS for burst extraction, e.g., required for oncology therapy known as FLASH method.

Figure 1: Left: The plot shows a typical time structure of a **non-optimized** beam current extracted by tune scan at GSI for a coasting beam (top) and improvements with bunching (bottom) inside the synchrotron; the full spill is shown in the insert. The sampling time is $\Delta t = 20 \mu s$. Right: The corresponding Fourier transformation is the averaged over 10 spills; reproduced from [1].

The temporal quality of slowly extracted beams from the synchrotron is crucial. At the medical ion centres, it significantly influences the patient treatment time and safety requirements; for the physics experiments at GSI and CERN, the maximum count rate of the users' detectors is significantly influenced. Within the project IFAST-REX (Work-Package 5.3, REX stands for Resonance slow EXtraction), we aimed to develop tools and technologies that significantly improve the spill micro-structure, i.e., fluctuations on the 100 μs time scale. Generally, the cause of the fluctuations is related to technical imperfections such as power supply ripples, with the main contributions from the

quadrupole power supply resulting in a variation of the particle tune. Figure 1 shows an example of a **non**-optimized fluctuating beam current extracted by a tune scan [1]. Moreover, the figure shows the improvement by bunching the beam in the synchrotron during the extraction. In a knock-out extraction, the stochastic excitation signal forming the diffusion process which acts as an additional influence to the spill micro-structure. Within IFAST-REX, mitigation strategies are developed to achieve a more uniform beam extraction to increase the treatment capability and fixed-target count rate homogeneity.

At the start of the project in the year 2021, five major topics for improvements were identified:

- Accelerator-physics considerations and beam dynamics simulations to mitigate the beam sensitivity to device imperfections
- Beam-based investigations to verify the simulation results and trigger more advanced simulations
- An extremely sensitive measurement for the AC variation of the power supply's current ΔI_{AC} with a resolution in the order of $\Delta I_{AC} / I_{DC} < 10^{-6}$ with respect to the DC current level
- An optimised excitation signal for the knock-out extraction to minimise the sensitivity to tune variations and to prevent periodic signal disturbances
- Improved beam instrumentation and beam control, including a feedback system for active extraction control.

The common effort of the experienced beneficiaries and associated partners was realised during the project time, specifically focusing on the scientific and technical issues. The beneficiaries are the scientific institutes CERN, GSI, and HIT, as well as the companies Barthel HF-Technik and Bergoz Instrumentation. The associated partners are CNAO, MedAustron, MIT and SEEIST. In relation to the change in their business model, MIT stepped out after the initial phase of the project. Figure 2 shows the logos of the participating institutions.

Figure 2: The logos of the beneficiaries and associated partners of IFAST-REX.

Various remote and personal meetings were organised during the project duration to discuss the scientific and technical issues, monitor the progress, and decide on further roadmaps. Common beam-based experiments were executed with the participation of experts from the involved institutions; more details are given below. Conference proceedings and referred journal publications directly related to the topic of IFAST-REX were published. A significant improvement of the micro-structure was clearly demonstrated based on accelerator-physics considerations, simulations and technical improvements. The task was executed in an intensive exchange between the accelerator laboratories and the involved industry. The initially foreseen goals were reached. The related methods are very general and can be applied at the participating accelerator facilities. Moreover, the development was documented in an in-person workshop co-organised by IFAST-REX partners leading to an intense knowledge transfer to the international community (see <https://indico.gsi.de/event/18184/>, 63 participating experts from Europe, Asia and America).

This report focuses on the innovative technical developments required for the improvement of slow extraction to document the progress related to the funding by the European Union. Two technical realisations are assigned as deliverables: Firstly, a system for extremely sensitive measurement of power supply current fluctuations in the frequency range 10 Hz to 40 kHz, and, secondly, a very versatile RF control and amplification chain providing a high-power of 500 W and large band width of 0.1 to 20 MHz for knock-out extraction. To document this novel technical solution, the report describes both systems produced by the industrial partners BergozTM Instrumentation and Barthel HF-Technik. The participating institutes performed extensive beam dynamics investigations in terms of analytical models and numerical simulations; they are briefly mentioned in this report, as most of them are well documented in referred articles. Beam-based experiments were performed at several facilities, partly as common efforts by personnel from several institutions. The results led to a significant increase in beam quality, which is now available for routine operation as this report will show for some examples; further results are published.

2 Facility Status in Year 2021 at Beginning of IFAST-REX

At the initial phase of IFAST in spring 2021, a remote two-day kick-off meeting in February 2021 was organised by GSI (see <https://indico.gsi.de/event/11868/>, 40 participants) to summarize the actual status concerning the micro-spill structure (100 μ s time scale) at the European slow extraction facilities. For the first time, a consistent comparison of the temporal beam quality produced using data sets from all facilities is evaluated by the same sample rate of 1 ms and a consistent analysis method. Figure 3 depicts the duty-factor F within $\Delta t = 10$ ms sample intervals describing the inverse of the fluctuations' standard deviation σ_c normalised to the mean extraction rate μ_c for the given sample time as

$$F_{\Delta t} = \frac{\mu_c^2}{\mu_c^2 + \sigma_c^2} < 1 \quad (\text{The larger the numerical value, the better the beam quality}).$$

A further statistical quantification is the coefficient of variance for the given sample time Δt , defined as

$$c_{V,\Delta t} = \frac{\sigma_c}{\mu_c} \quad (\text{The lower the numerical value, the better the beam quality});$$

the relation between the duty factor and coefficient of variance is $F_{\Delta t} = \frac{1}{1 + c_{V,\Delta t}^2}$. The plots show common features related to beam current fluctuations but also some differences between the participating facilities. Extraction of bunched beams in the frequency range of one to several MHz smooths the fluctuations significantly, see e.g. [1-3], and are used at the medical facilities for knock-out extraction. However, at CERN and GSI several experiments are sensitive to the related time structure in the range or faster than 0.1 to 1 μ s of the extracted beam which prevent for application at both institutes. Generally, the fluctuations are significantly larger than expected for a Poisson distribution at all facilities. The goal of IFAST-REX is to steer possible improvements through various beam manipulations, lattice parameter setting and innovative hardware. The extraction methods and numerical results at the facilities are summarized in Table 1.

The Fourier transformations, depicted in Figure 4, show narrow lines related to the 50 Hz net frequency caused by the magnet power supply switching as well as a broadband beam reaction which can be influenced by technical counteractions (such as air quadrupole operated in anti-phase to the main power supply switching) or by beam parameter settings (such as bunching, modification of the beam's momentum spread, or variation of the sextupole strength). Moreover, the excitation signal for knock-out extraction imprints some periodic structures. The plots of Figure 3 and Figure 4 show that comparable issues exist at all facilities, calling for a common effort to improve the beam quality. The smoothing of the extracted beam current, characterised by time and frequency domain methods, is the key challenge for the IFAST-REX Work-Package 5.3 to improve efficient beam delivery for patients and basic research. Therefore, the investigations of IFAST-REX comprise beam dynamics investigations, developing state-of-the-art technical devices with exceptional parameters and beam-based experimental verifications.

Figure 3: The duty factor F is shown for typical operational beams for several extraction methods at the IFAST-REX facilities. The duty factor concerns a readout time of $\Delta t = 1$ ms and evaluation time of $t_{eval} = 10$ ms; the red bars symbolise the average duty factor. On purpose, anonymous facility names are chosen; the data analysis was performed by F. Kuhtheubl (MedAustron).

Figure 4: Fourier transformations of a spill are shown for typical operational beams for several extraction methods at the participant facilities, calculated from the same data as in Figure 3.

Facility	A	B		C		D	E	F
Extraction method	tune scan	knock-out	Betatron core	tune scan	tune scan	knock-out	knock-out	knock-out
Beam structure	coasting	bunched	coasting	coasting	bunched	bunched	bunched	bunched
Foreseen improvement	empty-bucket channelling	air-core quad.	empty-bucket channelling	tune wobble	-	-	empty bucket channelling	air-core quad.
Aver. duty factor F_{10ms}	0.948	0.713	0.774	0.951	0.983	0.947	0.895	0.918

Table 1: Extraction methods, related average duty factor F and proposed improvements in year 2021 for the IFAST-REX facilities.

3 High Dynamic Range Current Measurement System

3.1 AIM AND GENERAL LAYOUT

Beam current fluctuations are partly caused by tune changes related to tiny ripples of the quadrupole power supplies. The measurement of such alternating-current (AC) fluctuations is defined as a technical deliverable within IFAST-REX. The realized device is a novel current measurement system for a high dynamic range determination of the power supply ripples, i.e., small current fluctuations ΔI_{AC} in the order of $\Delta I_{AC} / I_{DC} < 10^{-6}$ with respect to the direct-current (DC) I_{DC} of maximal 5 kA_{DC}. The device consists of two parts: Firstly, an active AC current transformer with at least 40 kHz bandwidth. Secondly, a precise compensation of the DC current is required to prevent magnetic core saturation due to the strong magnetic fields induced by the DC current. The DC-part is realised by a split ring core DC field measurement and compensation circuit. The technical functionality for typical power supplies was successfully demonstrated using a prototype (see below). A prototype realisation for current fluctuation measurements applicable to all IFAST-REX facilities is the project goal. In the future, such a system will be used as a feedback or feedforward system for power supply stabilisation. Table 2 summarises key specifications established at the beginning of the IFAST-REX project. The prototype, subject to this report, was specified for DC currents up to 5 kA.

Parameter	Abbreviation & condition	Value
DC current	I_{DC}	5 kA
AC current	I_{AC}	$\leq 1\% I_{DC}$
Measurement bandwidth	$\Delta f = f_{max} - f_{min}$	10 Hz – 40 kHz
Measurement resolution	$\Delta I_{AC}/I_{DC}$ for full bandwidth	$\sim 10^{-7}$
	$\Delta I_{AC}/I_{AC}$ for $10\text{Hz} < f < 40\text{kHz}$	$\sim 10^{-5}$
Measurement bandwidth	$\Delta f = f_{max} - f_{min}$	10 Hz – 40 kHz
Measurement accuracy	U_i/I_{AC}	$< 1\%$

Table 2: Key specifications of the high dynamic range current measurement system.

To achieve the required stabilisation of the magnet power supply currents, a current sensor was developed to detect current fluctuation $\Delta I_{AC} / I_{DC} < 10^{-6}$ with respect to the full-scale DC current. At a later stage after completion of IFAST-REX, it will be incorporated into the power supply control chain.

The requested resolution concerning the DC current is challenging to achieve. However, knowing that the AC current remains below 1% of the DC current allows to adapt the challenge by splitting it into two full-scale measurement ranges: For signals in the frequency range DC to 10 Hz, the measurement range must reach up to $I_{DC} \leq 5 \text{ kA}_{DC}$. For signals in the frequency range 10 Hz to 40 kHz, the measurement range must reach up to $1\% I_{DC}$. Consequently, the required resolution ΔI_{AC} with respect to the AC current is only $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{AC} (f > 10\text{Hz}) = 10^{-5}$, which is a reasonably relaxed requirement and is, in principle, achievable.

Despite emphasising the performance of AC current measurements and leaving DC current measurements mostly unspecified, DC currents of the required strength must be addressed. Their magnetic fields easily saturate any neighbouring magnetic materials. Thus, rendering, for example, the use of normal current transformers impossible. A viable solution is to add to the current transformer a DC compensation winding, which is driven by feedback electronics using a DC magnetic field sensor as schematically depicted in Figure 5. Such a DC compensation loop implies an accurate DC current measurement. That means a DC measurement will be available despite not being strictly required within this project.

Figure 5: General scheme for the combination of a DC transformer and an AC transformer to determine the AC component of the magnet current.

3.2 PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT

The prototype acts as a proof-of-principle at high DC currents $I_{DC} \leq 5kA_{DC}$. As such, it shall come close to the specifications of the high dynamic range current measurement system given in Table 2. A maximum DC current of 5 kA is considered sufficiently demanding to highlight the benefits of the tested solution.

A measurement scheme which has proven to be capable of highly accurate DC current measurements even in the multi-kA range is the closed-loop fluxgate DC current transformer (DCCT). However, since this project emphasises AC measurements, a different approach has been chosen.

The AC current transformer (ACCT) combines a passive current transformer with active electronics. It is widely used in particle accelerators for average current measurements of macro-pulses or chopped DC beams [3-5]. It has a measurement bandwidth of 1 Hz to 1 MHz and a resolution of about $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{AC} = 5 \times 10^{-5}$. Assuming a uniform noise spectrum, reduction of the ACCT bandwidth to the required 40 kHz limits noise to the specified $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{AC} = 1 \times 10^{-5}$ due to the scaling of the noise amplitude proportional to the square root of the measurement bandwidth Δf , i.e., $I_{noise} \propto \sqrt{\Delta f}$. To such an ACCT, a DC compensation winding shall be added, driven by feedback electronics. A commercial DC magnetic field probe (standard Hall sensor Honeywell SS495A1) is used to detect the strength of the magnetic field induced by the magnet power supply current. The DC magnetic field probe is placed in the gap of a split-ring core. A sketch and a photograph are shown in Figure 6. The DC and AC transformers are each equipped with a 1500-turn winding.

Figure 6: Sketch of the current sensor (left), photo of the open sensor case of the first prototype (middle) and the prototype on a power supply busbar at CERN (right).

A closed ring core is added to improve inductive coupling between primary and secondary currents. One coil is used for the DC feedback and one for the ACCT electronics.

The envisaged solution may seem simple and straightforward. However, achieving the required performance is challenging. The sensor resembles a three-winding transformer where the current to be measured acts as the primary winding. DC and very low-frequency signals shall circulate only in one secondary winding, higher frequencies only in the other. The transition between the two frequency ranges must be limited to a narrow frequency band to avoid that ramping of the DC current has a negative impact on the AC measurement. The ACCT output signal must be fed back into the feedback electronics to avoid resonances in this frequency region. Figure 7 shows the schematics of the solution.

Figure 7: Schematics of sensor and related electronics.

Furthermore, it is favourable if the spectral amplitude and phase relation of the two signals allow reconstituting a signal spanning the entire frequency range of DC to 40 kHz:

$$I_{DC-40kHz} = g_{DC}U_{DC-10Hz} + g_{AC}U_{10Hz-40kHz}$$

g_{DC} and g_{AC} are the calibration factors required to relate the output voltages $U_{DC-10Hz}$ and $U_{10Hz-40kHz}$ to the corresponding input currents.

The ACCT electronics are a copy of standard ACCT electronics [5], only adapted to fit current and frequency ranges. The feedback electronics were newly designed. The number of transformer winding turns is a compromise between, on the one hand, limiting feedback current and power loss in the coil and, on the other hand, limiting parasitic capacitance and high-frequency signal deformations. Models of transformers and electronics were created using Pathwave Advanced Design

System (ADS) and the Quite Universal Circuit Simulator (QUCS). Time-domain and frequency-domain simulations were performed to verify the characteristics and stability of the system.

3.3 FINAL PROTOTYPE

In 2023, the first prototype was tested at CERN with DC currents up to 5 kA_{DC}. These tests showed promising results and confirmed the principle, as reported in milestone report 2023. However, a couple of shortcomings were recognised. For example, a reference voltage was slightly wrong during these measurements, and DC current compensation would not work properly. While this error could be easily corrected, in-depth analysis of data taken at CERN and at Bergoz™ Instrumentation revealed the necessity to improve the electronics and the sensor.

For the first prototype electronics, the equipotentiality of the ground potential was the main issue. Highly sensitive circuits could be influenced by the strong DC feedback current being created nearby. Furthermore, high-frequency resonances in the MHz range could be observed under certain circumstances. For the first prototype sensor, the hysteresis of the split-ring core introduced a varying error in the hall probe measurements. A power loss due to compensation winding resistance would lead to excessive heating when running for long periods at maximum current.

All issues could be resolved by reviewing and improving the technical details of electronics and sensors. The final electronic and sensor hardware is depicted in Figure 8. The working principle and general engineering solution could remain unchanged.

Figure 8: Final prototype sensor and electronics.

3.4 MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Measurements with currents up to $I_{DC} = 5 \text{ kA}_{DC}$ were performed on a test stand at CERN dedicated to the highly accurate evaluation of high current measurement devices. A fluxgate DCCT is used as a reference measurement device. The test stand is optimised for DC and very slowly varying currents. Ramping to 5 kA_{DC} takes about 60 s. For our AC measurements, an additional cable was passed through the sensor parallel to the DC current busbar. An AC power amplifier injected AC currents up to a few amperes. Data was recorded by a 24-bit digitiser with up to 192 kS/s sampling rate. The digitizer's effective resolution of 19 effective number of bits (ENOB) is well sufficient for DC and AC measurements. Only in some data sets recorded for noise evaluation, the digitizer noise was non-

negligible. Generally, the digitizer’s absolute accuracy is of minor importance since DC and noise measurements are in comparison to the reference DCCT, while AC measurements are referenced to the voltage measured over a well-characterized 1Ω load resistor.

The DC current response was determined by ramping the primary current up to a fixed value, keeping it stable for some time and ramping it down again. Measurements were performed for flattop DC currents of -5 kA_{DC} , $-2.5\text{ kA}_{\text{DC}}$, -1 kA_{DC} , $+1\text{ kA}_{\text{DC}}$, $+2.5\text{ kA}_{\text{DC}}$ and $+5\text{ kA}_{\text{DC}}$. The sensor had to be turned over to change DC current polarity since the test stand only allows unipolar currents. Figure 9 shows the measured responses, and Figure 10 shows the deviation of the measured currents from the currents given by the reference fluxgate DCCT. All deviations remain within $\pm 1\text{ A}$, which is within the project requirements. At $\pm 5\text{ kA}_{\text{DC}}$, a slow drift can be observed due to the heating of the electronics, especially the load resistors of the DC compensation current. In a later test, a fan was added that actively cooled the electronics which considerably reduced the drift.

Figure 9: Measured currents for different nominal DC values.

Figure 10: Deviation of measured currents from the reference measurements.

The AC current response was measured at DC offset currents of -5 kA_{DC} , $-2.5\text{ kA}_{\text{DC}}$, -1 kA_{DC} , 0 A_{DC} , $+1\text{ kA}_{\text{DC}}$, $+2.5\text{ kA}_{\text{DC}}$ and $+5\text{ kA}_{\text{DC}}$. The AC current reference is established by measuring voltage on

a $1\ \Omega$ load resistor. All results are shown in Figure 11. They mostly overlap, as expected for a well-working system. Minor differences towards high frequencies are probably due to the manipulation when turning the sensor for a change of DC polarity. Curves for negative DC currents and zero overlap, as do the curves for positive DC currents. These measurements agree with expectations from simulations. The AC part spans a bandwidth from 8 Hz to above 40 kHz, thus fulfilling the project specifications as given in Table 2.

Figure 11: Feedback (blue) and ACCT (green) frequency responses at different DC offset currents from $-5\ \text{kA}_{\text{DC}}$ to $5\ \text{kA}_{\text{DC}}$. Within the depicted scale, all curves mostly overlap.

Data allowing the evaluation of measurement system noise was recorded for 5 s at 192 kS/s sampling rate during stable DC currents. To obtain a better voltage resolution with the digitiser, its input channels were switched to AC coupled mode, effectively removing any signal frequency below 0.8 Hz, including the signal due to the DC primary current. Figure 12 (left) shows the noise spectra at $0\ \text{A}_{\text{DC}}$ primary current, and Figure 12 (right) shows the noise spectra at $5\ \text{kA}_{\text{DC}}$ primary current.

The noise of the reference DCCT and noise of the newly developed system are plotted. To calculate a noise spectrum covering the full spectral range, the DC output was low-pass filtered at 2 kHz and summed to the AC output. Above $\sim 100\ \text{Hz}$, the DC output noise is limited by digitiser noise. The low-pass filter prevents this digitizer noise from becoming visible in the sum. However, due to some crosstalk between AC and DC outputs, tighter filtering than 2 kHz is not beneficial.

Both frequency spectra of Figure 12 show narrow lines at 50 Hz and its harmonics. Moreover, lines appear at 73 Hz and its harmonics. They are present in both measurement systems. Those lines are induced by the primary current or the measurement environment. 73 Hz is the excitation frequency of the reference DCCT. Spectral lines above 10 kHz are probably due to the ripple in the electronics power supply. Their origin was not further investigated. Since the reference DCCT has 16 kHz bandwidth, its noise spectrum rolls off above this frequency.

Figure 12: Noise spectrum of data acquired zero A_{DC} current (left) stable 5 kA_{DC} current (right). Reference DCCT (red) and novel sensor (blue).

Below ~ 10 Hz, the reference DCCT shows less noise than the newly developed system. Above ~ 10 Hz, the new system shows significantly less noise, which was the objective of its development. At zero DC current, the total noise of the new system could be evaluated to < 2 mA_{rms} when neglecting spectral lines common to both measurement systems. With a 5 kA_{DC} current, total noise could be evaluated to be < 4 mA_{rms} when neglecting spectral lines and the low-frequency behaviour common to both measurement systems. Below a frequency of ~ 60 Hz both systems show very similar noise, which indicates that the primary current was fluctuating. The primary current cannot fluctuate at higher frequencies because of the inductance of the load. Since environmental noise and fluctuations of the primary current could not be perfectly identified and compensated, this noise evaluation gives an upper limit for the real system noise. For technical reasons, higher current could not be applied.

To reduce impact of the measurement environment, noise measurements were repeated at Bergoz™ Instrumentation. However, as before, environmental noise and fluctuations of the primary current could not be perfectly identified and compensated. Without DC current, total noise could be evaluated to < 1.5 mA_{rms} , i.e., $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{DC} \leq 3 \times 10^{-7}$ with respect to 5 kA_{DC} full scale. With 1 kA_{DC} current, total noise could be evaluated to < 2 mA_{rms} , i.e., $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{DC} \leq 4 \times 10^{-7}$ with respect to 5 kA_{DC} full scale. For technical reasons, currents higher than 1 kA_{DC} could not be tested at Bergoz™ Instrumentation.

3.5 CONCLUSION FOR HIGH DYNAMIC RANGE CURRENT MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

In-depth analysis of measurements performed in 2023 with a first prototype allowed to identify some shortcomings which were considered when developing a second prototype. The second prototype was tested and compared to a reference DCCT at CERN in January 2025 showing considerably better results. The measurement system was working correctly for DC currents up to 5 kA_{DC} . The response over the full AC bandwidth remained stable at any DC current level. Measurement results show that the system fulfils the specifications determined at the start of the IFAST-REX collaboration. Most notably, a resolution of $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{DC} < 10^{-6}$ was achieved with a measurement bandwidth of 10 Hz – 40 kHz, leading to completion of the related technical task.

Despite fulfilling project specifications in its current state, some deficiencies were recognised, which may merit further technical improvements; however, no general performance limitations exist as deficiencies concerns only the upper specification limits, which are seldomly reached. When operating the transformer for long durations at the maximal specified DC current of 5 kA_{DC}, electronics heats up. While this could be resolved by adding a fan, such a solution may also add electromagnetic noise, thus reducing measurement resolution. Other solutions will be investigated. Furthermore, some crosstalk is present between the DC feedback electronics and the AC measurement electronics and can be optimised. Additionally, some improvements in electromagnetic noise immunity and better filtering of power supply noise are foreseen for the final design but are now a technical challenge. The goal of all these improvements is to achieve higher reliability without impacting performance.

Summary: A system for the measurement of the AC component of a power supply current was developed based on the novel combination of an AC transformer (bandwidth 10 Hz to 40 kHz) and a DC transformer used for the compensation of magnetic torus saturation. The achieved resolution $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{DC} < 10^{-6}$ is extraordinary for magnet power supply measurements. The system is now ready for installation at the busbar connected to typical power supplies. The reached Technology Readiness Level is TRL 7 which is one level higher as originally expected. The next step, following the IFAST-REX task, is to incorporate the measurement system as a sensor for a feedback circuit of the power supply regulation.

4 RF Signal Generation for knock-out Extraction

4.1 GENERAL PROPERTIES FOR KNOCK-OUT SIGNAL GENERATION

The second technical system serving as a deliverable within IFAST-REX concerns the knock-out extraction scheme and its hardware realisation comprising the generation of custom excitation waveforms, along with high-performance amplifiers and eventually a matching network. A correlation between the micro-structure and the knock-out excitation signal was previously reported from Japanese facilities [6-10]; these investigations were systematically enlarged during IFAST-REX and particularly supported by beam dynamics studies leading to a deeper understanding of the related accelerator physics. As a first step, the required parameters for an optimised knock-out extraction scheme were investigated with analytic beam-dynamics methods, versatile simulations, and extensive beam-based measurements at the partners' facilities as summarised in Chapter 5. In the actual chapter, we describe the development of a high-performance commercial digital-analogue conversion module based on Software Defined Radio principles used for the low-level RF signal generation. Complex waveforms adequate for an improved extraction scheme can be generated using the software GNU-Radio; see below. A high-performance RF amplifier was realised within IFAST-REX to drive the exciter plates and a possible matching network. The amplifier's main peculiarity is related to the combination of wide bandwidth, high output power, and operation connected to an unmatched load, leading to the requirement for operation with significant power reflection as described below.

The medical facilities HIT and MIT use exclusively knock-out extraction; at CNAO and MedAustron, knock-out is implemented in addition to other extraction methods. At GSI tune scan or knock-out extraction can be used. The power requirements for the transverse excitation are comparable at those facilities. For CERN PS, knock-out extraction was performed, and the technique has been operationally implemented for the extraction of low-energy heavy ions within the CHIMERA/HEARTS project [11,12]. At the CERN SPS, a hybrid extraction scheme was tested, where knock-out extraction was added to the nominal chromatic extraction scheme to improve spill quality [13]. For the signal specification of slow knock-out extraction, it is beneficial to recall the involved multi-step process comprising the following processes:

- In the first step, the horizontal machine tune is transferred close to a 3rd-order resonance, i.e., the fractional part of the tune is close to 1/3 or 2/3. The beam motion is unstable above a certain amplitude for a given tune by the action of sextupole fields and the related non-linear dynamics. The border between the unstable and stable regions is referred to as the separatrix.
- In a diffusion process, a transverse excitation is applied to randomly drive the particles' betatron amplitude from the beam core towards the separatrix.
- When particles cross the separatrix, their betatron amplitudes grow exponentially. The increase continues until the particles reach the septum, where an additional kick results in the passage through the extraction channel. The duration between the separatrix crossing and the arrival at the extraction septum is referred to as transit time.
- Any power supply ripple leads to a variation of the beam's closed orbit (caused by dipoles), the separatrix phase space location and size (caused by quadrupoles), or the excitation strength

of the non-linear forces (caused by sextupoles). As the final effect, power supply ripples result in a burst of particles or a break of the extracted beam current.

- Moreover, the knock-out signals' properties strongly influence particle motion during diffusion and separatrix crossing.

For the specification of the RF signal spectrum and power requirements for knock-out excitation, a detailed understanding of the extraction process is required and had been worked out within the IFAST duration. The investigations based on advanced beam-physics methods and its experimental verification are described in Chapter 5.

As used below, we define the excitation spectrum: The central excitation frequency f_{excite} is related to the horizontal betatron frequency $f_{\beta} = Q_x \cdot f_{\text{rev}}$, respectively the tune Q_x by the relation $f_{\text{excite}} = (h \pm q_x) \cdot f_{\text{rev}}$ where f_{rev} is the revolution frequency of the particles in the synchrotron and q_x is the non-integer part of the horizontal tune; $h \in \mathbb{N}$ is the harmonic number of the excitation and \pm refers to the lower or upper sideband, respectively. $h = 0$ is referred to as baseband. To enable a diffusion process, a band of finite width Δf_{excite} around the central frequency is applied.

4.2 RF CONTROL TECHNICAL SOLUTION EXAMPLE

As an integral part of IFAST-REX, a low-level signal generator for the transverse knock-out excitation was developed for prototyping at HIT [14] and later commissioned with a larger diagnostic scope at GSI SIS-18 and GSI-ESR [15] as well as at MedAustron [16,17]. A novel approach for accelerators is taken using a Software Defined Radio (SDR) system and the open-source GNU-Radio software [18]. The transceiver technology implements digital signal processing in software, thus allowing for a low-cost yet highly flexible setup for creating customisable and tuneable excitation spectra. The GNU-Radio software is used for the graphical design of signal processing flow graphs and control of signal parameters. Due to its open-source nature, it has the potential for long-term maintainability and integration at several facilities. Furthermore, this opens up the possibility of sharing algorithms for generating waveforms across accelerator facilities. [15]

SDR technology is widely used in radio communication systems and has potential applications in many fields. An SDR typically consists of a front-end with ADCs and DACs, and a backend performing the digital signal processing (DSP). A universal software radio peripheral (USRP) was used as an off-the-shelf front-end to generate the RF signals. For the implementation of the DSP, the open-source GNU-Radio framework [18] was chosen, which allows a graphical design of the signal processing flow graphs. The extensive flexibility and low modification efforts make the device a natural choice for prototyping [14-16], experiments, and also regular use in the accelerator environment. As GNU-Radio is open software, a custom out-of-tree (OOT) module comprising the blocks and signal processing logic required to apply SDR technology in an accelerator environment has been implemented and published for common use [28]. This includes a block related to decreasing trigger delays and loopback latency of GNU-Radio.

Figure 13 depicts the working principle of the signal generator for knock-out extraction. The USRP digitises the signal of a particle detector measuring the spill intensity and receives the trigger (TTL pulse) via the general-purpose input/outputs (GPIOs). It streams the data via PCIe to an industrial PC, where GNU-Radio performs the DSP. The generated signals are streamed back to the USRP and

delivered via a Digital Analogue Converter (DAC) at the RF port. The Ettus model X310 with the low-frequency daughter boards was used. In principle, the installed DACs provide sampling rates of up to 200 MS/s with 16-bit resolution and the daughter boards are rated DC to 30 MHz, corresponding to typically about the 30th harmonics of the revolution frequency f_{rev} . Such high frequencies might not be required in practice; however, beam experiments show a spill structure improvement with excitations up to several tens of MHz. This model is now used to control the knock-out extraction amplifier at GSI. MedAustron uses the same control hardware with a slightly different setup; see [16] for more details.

Figure 13: Signal generation scheme (left) and universal software radio peripheral hardware (right); reproduced from Ref. [15].

Figure 14: GNU Radio flow graph for the generation of a knock-out signal at baseband (left) and the frequency spectrum for three excitation types generated by the branches of the flow graph (right); reproduced from Ref. [15].

Figure 14 (left) depicts a basic example of the generation of excitation signals to show the capability of the GNU-Radio software and programming style. Three basic signal types have been implemented for this example: Firstly, a signal phase modulated by a binary sequence randomly flipping between ± 1 , referred to as random binary phase-shift keying (BPSK, top left box); secondly, a band-filtered uniform white noise (middle left box); thirdly, a sinusoidal frequency modulated sine resulting in a frequency chirp (lower left box). The baseband signal is up-sampled, and the frequency is shifted to the betatron frequency, i.e., the desired sidebands of the revolution frequency f_{rev} . Figure 14 (right) shows the resulting frequency spectrum of these three signals centred around the betatron frequency. More complex signal chains can be created comparably with reasonable effort and were realised and

are now applied during regular operation at GSI; more details, including more complex signal generations, are described in [14,15,19-24,28].

4.3 RF SIGNAL OPTIMISATION BY BEAM-BASED MEASUREMENTS

4.3.1 Knock-Out Micro-Structure Optimisation at COSY, GSI and HIT

As stated above, the GNU-Radio software allows for very versatile signal generation. Very detailed beam-based experiments were jointly performed at GSI, HIT and COSY (Forschungszentrum Jülich). It aimed to generate the most appropriate signal shape for a smooth spill micro-structure. Accelerator physics investigations related to the analytical solution of the Kobayashi-Hamiltonian [23] and extensive beam-dynamics simulations preceded the experimental investigations; those topics are briefly described in Chapter 5. In the actual paragraph, we show the results of experimental investigations at COSY and discuss the consequences for the RF amplifier. The excitation at the baseband of the betatron oscillation can be accompanied by excitations at several harmonics as generated by the GNU-Radio software. Several precursor investigations were done at HIT and GSI and are reported in [3,14,15,19-22].

Figure 15: Left: Example of an extracted spill at COSY (Forschungszentrum Jülich) showing a zoom of 250 ms duration for three different excitation schemes. Right: The composition of multi-band excitation signals; reproduced from Ref. [23] where more details are described.

Figure 16: Left: The spill quality, characterised by the duty factor and the coefficient of variance for the investigated multi-band excitation signals tabulated in Figure 15; the sample time is $\Delta t = 50\mu s$. Right: The required power levels for the multi-band excitation signals; reproduced from Ref. [23] where more details are described.

We refer here to the publication [23] where various schemes were tested at COSY, as displayed in Figure 15 and Figure 16. The properties of the spill micro-structure depend significantly on the excitation signal: A single baseband excitation leads to a spiky structure with large fluctuations (band-limited noise, grey curve); adding band-limited noise at two harmonics leads to a moderate soothing (referred to as 3 Noise, yellow curve); a further smoothing can be achieved by adding a sine wave at the harmonics (referred to as Noise++, blue curve) as it leads to a faster crossing of the separatrix. Further signal types, as referred to in the table, were tested, and their influence is described in [23]. Figure 16 shows the duty factor and the coefficient of variance for the different signal types; the signal type Noise++ shows the best performance in the sense of low fluctuations.

A further relevant ingredient is the RF power to extract all stored particles completely. As displayed in Figure 16, the power requirements differ significantly. A noise signal is required to efficiently diffuse the stored particle from the beam core towards the separatrix, followed by relatively long-lasting excitation to betatron amplitudes that cross the separatrix. The required RF power for the baseband noise is relatively low. Adding sine waves at harmonics, as realised for Noise++, leads to a fast separatrix crossing but requires higher RF power. The excitation by only three sine waves is inefficient for the diffusion process and calls for even higher RF power. Other signal types have intermediate RF power requirements. In summary, the signal type Noise++ shows the best performance for the spill micro-structure with moderate RF power requirements.

Recently, experiments were conducted at HIT and GSI to investigate the beam reaction to the excitation at higher harmonics of the betatron frequency [26] to compare the experimental results to simulations. As the first step, single bands were excited up to harmonics $h = 10$ for the lower and upper sidebands. Compared to the baseband excitation with a typical coefficient of variance $c_V \approx 1$ (corresponding to a duty factor $F = 0.5$, sample time $\Delta t = 50 \mu\text{s}$), the micro-structure improves for higher harmonics, e.g., for harmonics $h = 10$ to typically $c_V \approx 0.4$ (corresponding to a duty factor $F = 0.86$). The exact value of the coefficient of variance depends on various beam and accelerator optics parameters such as the momentum spread and chromaticity (leading to a variation of the chromatics tune spread), which are systematically different for the lower and upper sidebands. In the second step, a multi-band excitation up to a given harmonics was applied, which improves the spill quality compared to the single-band of the same harmonics. More details on the experiment and its interpretation are collected in [26]. Following the above-mentioned considerations, it can be concluded concerning the technical realization that an RF control and amplifier with large bandwidth is required. The related technical solution was realized within the IFAST-REX with an RF chain with a bandwidth 0.1 to 20 MHz, larger than the previously used hardware.

4.3.2 Knock-Out macro-structure Feedback System

To control the extracted particle rate, the amplitude of the excitation signal must be increased during the spill, as particles must diffuse from the beam core to the separatrix. Basically, a fast exponential decrease in the beginning of the extraction, followed by a slow exponential increase during the extraction duration is required. The RF amplitude can be controlled by a feedforward control for the coarse power requirement, but to accomplish the optimal macro-structure, an active stabilisation via a feedback system is required to ensure a constant extraction rate. A software-controlled feedback loop operating in the SDR was realised at GSI to control the uniformity of the extracted current on the 10 ms time scale [24,27,28], as schematically depicted in Figure 17. The actual particle extraction

rate is measured by a detector mounted in front of the target; it can be a scintillator providing single particle counting or an ionisation chamber equipped with sufficient fast electronics. Due to the different types of experiments, various detectors are used and must be adapted to the input of the SDR. At medical facilities, a standard ionisation chamber for patient intensity monitoring can be used, which simplifies the system. Using a modern optimisation algorithm available in Python, the optimal PID regulation parameters for the feedback can be adjusted within 10 to 30 successive extractions [27-29].

Figure 17: Scheme of the feedback system at GSI using the Universal Software Radio controlled by GNU Radio software scale [24,27,28].

The low-level signal chain acts as the input for the RF power amplifier, providing sufficient bandwidth and power required for the knock-out extraction. Figure 18 summarises the commissioning of the combined macro- and micro-structure control: The left plot shows a 5 s extraction where an almost rectangular macro-structure can be created providing significantly less micro-structure fluctuations compared to an uncontrolled extraction [24,29]. The right plot shows the time evolution of RF power with a gross exponential growth related to the diffusion of the core particle and some wiggles related to the action of the feedback system.

Figure 18: Left: Commissioning results for the feedback system at GSI to generate a constant macro-structure. Right: The corresponding RF power during the extraction. The feedforward signal comprises of two exponential functions [24,29].

Presently, the described hardware and software devices are being implemented into the standard control system at GSI usable for regular operation. Typical nuclear physics experiments at GSI can

benefit significantly, leading to a typical factor ≈ 2 increase in the achievable statistical accuracy for the same duration of target irradiation; this is a significant improvement for most of the users at GSI. In principle, the described control solution for the knock-out extraction could be adapted for all facilities of the IFAST-REX consortium with some adaption related to legal aspects of medical facilities. The macro-structure feedback system was also adapted to make it available for tune scan driven slow extraction; this extraction method is used part-time at CERN and GSI.

A precursor feedback system was implemented at HIT some years ago [30] using in-house electronics and is used during regular patient treatment. However, the feedback input uses the standard patient monitor, allowing a more straightforward adaptation of the feedback's actual value. During the IFAST-REX project duration, the system was renewed and is described in the next section.

4.3.3 Knock-Out Direct Digital Synthesis at HIT

For the medical accelerator at HIT, a new version of Knock-Out Direct Digital Synthesis (KO DDS) was developed to fit into the central control system, fulfil the requirements for the fast switch-off medical interlock system and increase the availability and reliability compared to a PC software solution. The excitation is performed at several frequency bands, as described in the SDR solution. An in-house system is required as open software cannot be implemented for patient treatment due to German legal regulations.

Figure 19: Block diagram of the KO DDS v2. Each of the four DDS paths consists of a noise generator, a DDS, a DAC and a logarithmic amplifier. The four signals are combined in a sum amplifier, filtered and amplified. An RF switch at the end can switch off the signal in case of an external interlock.

The design of KO DDS v2 is based on the outcome of a recent master thesis [31] and a publication [20,21]. As depicted in Figure 19, the KO DDS v2 generates an RF signal with up to four different frequencies, each of which can be broadened in the spectrum with the Pseudo Random Noise - Phase Shift Keying (PRN-PSK) method. For each of the four frequencies, an amplitude can be specified. The four frequency paths operate independently and the signals are added. An RF switch turns off the RF signal under certain conditions. This PRN-PSK signal type delivers sufficient smooth micro-structure for the application at HIT.

The KO DDS v2 consists of two boards: the motherboard with FPGA for communication with the control system and the daughter board with the RF front end and the interlock system. The KO DDS v2 daughter board has four independent DDS (AD9835), four logarithmic amplifiers (LMH6502), one combiner, and two amplifier stages. Furthermore, for patient treatment safety regulations, there is a fibre optic interlock circuit for spill pause and an external medical interlock on the board, which drives a fast RF switch. An example of a generated signal is shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Figure 20: Left: KO DDS v2 hardware produced for HIT. Right: An example of a time domain signal with three frequencies (time axis 200 ns/div).

Figure 21: Example of a spectrum of the KO DDS v2 with two frequency bands.

4.4 RF AMPLIFIER DESIGN

The specification of the RF amplifier is based on the above-described beam-based investigations. It demands a multi-band excitation and high-power output related to the random superposition of independent signals. As beam dynamics simulation and experimental verification were part of IFAST-REX, the specifications for the RF amplifier were started later than initially anticipated; however, the final realisation was achieved on time.

Figure 22 shows a photo of the final RF amplifier manufactured by the IFAST-REX beneficiary Bathel HF-Technik. Two units were produced to enable a parallel operation of the two exciter plates in a push-pull mode, as schematically shown in Figure 13. Table 3 collects the basic specifications and achievements. Technically, we chose a bandwidth from 100 kHz to 20 MHz; the lower boundary is related to the baseband betatron frequency at injection energy for large synchrotrons such as SIS18, and the upper boundary enables at least the 10th harmonics of the betatron frequency after acceleration. The amplification is 56 to 58 dB providing an output power of up to 500 W into a 50 Ω termination. The achieved gain flatness is exceptionally stable, providing only a variation of 2 dB on the entire bandwidth and an input power variation of 30 dB, as displayed in Figure 23. Full power

cw-operation was tested, and only a decrease of the output power by 0.4 dB after 700 s was determined as related to thermal drifts, see Figure 24. The typical duty cycle is related to a 1 to 10 s long extraction with increasing power followed by a break of typically 1 s for the beam injection and acceleration; the thermal stability of the RF amplifier is suited for this operation mode. Due to the large bandwidth, harmonic distortions range up to -15 dBc. However, this does not influence significantly the usage because a noise component is required for the particle diffusion from the core to the periphery.

Figure 22: The RF amplifier realised as a 19" device.

Figure 23: Gain flatness curves for various frequencies measured with the RF amplifier and 50 Ω termination.

Parameter	Value	Remark
Frequency range	0.1 ... 20 MHz	Extreme broadband
Output power	500 W	High-power output
Duty cycle	CW operation with full output power Typical: Operation up to 10 s followed by ≈ 1 s break	Related to the extraction duration
Gain	57 ... 60 dB	
Gain flatness	Lower than 2 dB	Good gain flatness
Input impedance	50 Ω	
Input reflection VSWR	< 1.2:1	
Amplifier output impedance	50 Ω	Can be operated with any load impedance
Output reflection VSWR	< 3:1	
Capacitive load of exciter electrodes (typical value)	≈ 50 pF and voltage transformation ratio of 1:5	Reflected power from capacitive load
Load impedance range	Inductive and capacitive load possible	Can drive an inductive matching network
2 nd harmonics distortion	-35 ... -15 dBc	Acceptable value
Cooling and acoustic noise	Air, < 70 dBA	
Mechanics	19" rack mount	

Table 3: Basic specifications as achieved for the power amplifier.

Figure 24: Stability measurement for 400 W operation at 20 MHz into 50 Ω load over a time of 700 s; the decrease of the gain is only 0.4 dB.

At HIT, detailed bench tests of the RF amplifier were executed. Beam-based tests were performed at HIT and GSI to benefit from the large bandwidth and high power used for the excitation of high betatron frequency harmonics [26].

The peculiarity of the RF amplifier is the free choice of load impedance, which can lead to a significant reflected power as special precautions are implemented to prevent the destruction of the high-power stage. Three possible configurations are common for the connection to the exciter electrodes:

- A 50 Ω termination is used at the output port of the stripline electrodes in 50 Ω geometry. This configuration prevents reflections; however, the matched impedance limits the achievable voltage for the beam deflection.
- A pure capacitive coupling by the connection to only one port of the stripline; This configuration enhances the deflecting voltage but leads to almost 100 % reflection.
- A specially designed inductive matching network to enlarge the voltage by the transformer winding ratio can be considered. As in the capacitive coupling configuration, reflections occur. Moreover, the frequency-dependent damping related to the transformer core material losses might weaken the achievable deflection voltage. A system design realised at a Japanese medical facility is described in [32] and can serve as a guideline.

At HIT, the 50 Ω case is realised for the beam-based amplifier tests. However, at GSI, the high beam rigidity calls for a larger deflecting voltage which is realized by a pure capacitive coupling by direct connection to the electrodes. Alternatively, a matching network can be used to increase the plate voltage for the beam deflection. The challenge for this matching network is the extremely wide bandwidth range from 0.1 to 20 MHz, providing a sufficient flat transmission characteristic as the matching conditions depend on the capacitive load by the electrodes. For this bandwidth interval, the power absorption by the ferrite cores is frequency dependent, leading to a temperature change and, hence, a permeability modification. Considerations concerning such matching networks are ongoing but are outside of the IFAST-REX scope.

4.5 CONCLUSION CONCERNING RF-CONTROL AND AMPLIFIER

All consortium members executed detailed beam dynamics simulations for the non-linear extraction process, and relevant beam-based investigations were performed for their verification. The final goal is tailoring the optimal excitation spectrum for a smooth diffusion and a uniform separatrix crossing.

A high-performance commercial solution using the SDR is available for generating complex signal spectra, accompanied by an adequate, user-friendly software control via GNU Radio. Complex signal types with multi-band characteristics can be generated efficiently. The system enables dedicated beam-based experiments, which significantly increases knowledge of the related beam dynamics and significantly improves the micro-structure. The same low-level system can be used as a feedback system for the spill macro-structure with about 10 ms regulation time. At MedAustron, a comparable system is installed for beam-based experiments. As an alternative, an in-house signal generator was realised at HIT.

A 500 W high-power RF amplifier of broad bandwidth was realised with well-balanced further performances. The RF amplifier peculiarity is related to the immunity to reflections, allowing an operation with an arbitrary load impedance.

The described system at HIT and GSI could serve as a prototype for the implementation at the other consortium facilities: At MedAustron [16,33] and CNAO [34,35], bunched knock-out extraction is considered as an alternative to the presently realised longitudinal manipulation for coasting beams by betatron-core and empty-bucket channelling extraction as it allows efficient for multi-energy extraction. At CERN PS, knock-out extraction has proved extremely useful for the extraction of low-energy ions, as it allows for fine control of the extraction rate at multiple energies. In the PS and SPS proton operation, due to the high beam rigidity, knock-out extraction might not be appropriate as the main driving mechanism, but can be applied on top of the main chromatic scheme to improve spill quality. Other RF techniques such as empty-bucket channelling are also employed in this context. The beam excitation system has further advanced applications beyond slow extraction, such as beam parameter measurements [19], transverse dampers [36] and advanced diagnostic tools [37].

The engineering design for knock-out excitation is finished, and its functionality has been proven experimentally. The Technical Readiness Level is TRL 7 which is one level higher than originally foreseen.

5 Beam Dynamics Achievements and Experimental Verifications

5.1 BEAM DYNAMICS FOR KNOCK-OUT MICRO-STRUCTURE IMPROVEMENTS

Beam dynamics studies are the basis of any improvement in accelerator operation. During the entire duration of IFAST-REX, extensive studies were performed by consortium members at all participating facilities. The studies comprise analytical considerations, in most cases based on the Kobayashi-Hamiltonian [25] to approximate the non-linear beam dynamics. Versatile particle tracking simulations were executed using the new Python-based framework Xsuite [38,39] by most consortium members, leading to an intense exchange of code and experience. The code is optimized for particle tracking using GPUs, which enables the simulation of many particles as required for the time-dependent parameter changes during slow extraction. The code includes versatile features traditionally distributed on several standard simulation codes. Moreover, Xsuite is an open software project, and authors can propose and implement additional features. During IFAST-REX, features related to the simulation of the knock-out extraction process have been implemented and contributed to the Xsuite framework. This includes an element to model the beam excitation process, as well as several monitors to record and assess the particle dynamics behaviour during the extraction.

A different approach is related to the usage of Henon maps [40,41] to calculate the beam evolution on a turn-by-turn basis.

Even though simulations constitute a significant part of the IFAST-REX project, only a brief overview of recent achievements concerning the spill micro-structure by consortium members is given in the following two sections, pointing to selected publications. The topic is well documented in conference proceedings and reviewed journals; the reader is referred to those articles. Most publications contain simulations and experimental verifications focusing on the dedicated properties at one facility. However, most improvement methods can be adapted to other facilities. We focus on knock-out extraction in this section. In the following section, citations related to other methods, such as tune scan, betatron-core extraction and empty-bucket channelling, are briefly addressed.

Figure 25: Normalized Hamiltonian distribution of the particle before their respective extraction, simulated for different excitation signals as shown in Figure 15. The average Hamiltonian is plotted as a white dashed line. The red dashed lines mark the separatrices. Right: Time derivative for the three excitation types in the close vicinity of the separatrix represents the separatrix crossing speed. Plots are reproduced from [23].

One example of tracking simulation results is depicted in Figure 25 and is related to the discussion of experimental results shown above in Figure 15 and Figure 16 for measurements at COSY [23]. It concerns the spill quality for different excitation signal types, providing fewer fluctuations for the type Noise++. In the simulation, the particle extension is represented by the value of the Hamiltonian and its time evolution shortly before extraction. Shortly before reaching instability, the distance to the separatrix is largest for the sinusoidal type, and the crossing speed is maximal; however, pure sinusoidal signals would require a much larger power to extract all stored particles. For the type Noise++ comprising a broadband noise signal and two sinusoidal contributions, the depicted distance of the particles prior to extraction is large, and the crossing speed is comparable; however, a significantly lower power for extracting all stored particles is required. Large values for the distance to the separatrix and the crossing speed make the beam less sensitive to variation of the separatrix caused by power supply fluctuations (in the visualization corresponding to a vertical movement of the red lines), leading to the particles' transition to the unstable phase area above the red line. A large distance to the separatrix corresponds to a well-controlled and, hence, smooth micro-structure. This explanation aligns with the experimental observation; it acts as an example of a general model required for the discussed improvements; the methods and more results are described in [23]. The experiment at COSY was based on precursor investigations at HIT, where a correlation between the micro-structure and excitation signal type was experimentally demonstrated and supported by simulations [20,31].

An accurate modelling of the stored beam reaction is required for the tailored knock-out excitation signal. Several theoretical and experimental campaigns were conducted at HIT and GSI to determine the tune distribution shortly before the extraction when the beam is stored close to the 3rd-order resonance [19,21,42,43]. The beam transfer function (BTF) is determined by exciting the beam to gentle coherent betatron oscillations by a frequency chirp and recorded beam response. A significant modification for the regular BTF tune spectrum is recorded and confirmed by tracking simulations. This can be explained by a modified horizontal phase space distribution related to the non-linear contributions of the sextupole fields described by the modification of the Hamiltonian. The topic by itself is interesting, as it acts as an example of non-linear beam response. Concerning the knock-out extraction, the action of the different signal types can be designed according to the beam distribution, we refer to the given citations for more details.

At MedAustron, the knock-out extraction was investigated from a theoretical and experimental perspective and advantages compared to other methods are weighted [16,33,44]. Besides analytical results, tracking simulations with different codes are compared and experimental investigations for various excitation signals are described in the related PhD thesis [44]. Moreover, the thesis contains the implementation of a knock-out extraction scheme at MedAustron. The main topic is the comparison of different extraction methods; besides knock-out, the thesis describes the property of betatron-core acceleration [35] and empty-bucket channelling [16]. The particle transit to the unstable phase space area is related to longitudinal manipulations and chromatic coupling between momentum spread and tune. In particular, empty-bucket channelling enables a fast particle approach towards the separatrix, leading to insensitivity to quadrupole current fluctuations. At CNAO, the initially installed betatron-core extraction [35] is now accompanied by a knock-out extraction scheme [34]; empty-

bucket channelling serves as a third option. Both medical facilities cooperate on slow extraction hardware realization and performance optimization.

At SEEIIST and its follow-up synchrotron projects, knock-out and tune-scan extraction are considered as described in the related PhD thesis [45]. Detailed simulations for the next generation of medical synchrotrons concern several aspects of slow extraction. As the researchers are hosted at CERN, they worked closely together on these projects. In particular, the collaboration concerns the development of solutions for the Next Ion Medical Machine Study (NIMMS) activities and the studies at the CERN PS to investigate the use of octupoles for extraction improvements. Moreover, SEEIIST scientists had an intense collaboration with MedAustron, HIT, and GSI and participated in several experiments and their related data interpretation.

5.2 FURTHER STUDIES ON MICRO-STRUCTURE IMPROVEMENTS

Empty-bucket channelling is an appropriate method for counteracting power supply ripples. The method is based on a scan of a slightly detuned bunching frequency compared to the revolution frequency. The frequency scan accelerates a subset of particles. Via chromatic tune shift, the resonance condition for extraction is reached for the subset and results in a fast separatrix crossing; therefore, the sensitivity to power supply ripples is low, as argued above for Figure 25. During the project duration, intense efforts were conducted at CERN, and the system is now operational at SPS in connection to the Constant Optics Slow Extraction COSE [46]. Very detailed beam dynamics simulations and measurements are published as conference proceedings [11,47,48], in refereed journals [49], and as a PhD thesis [50]. The dependencies of the micro-structure related to power supply ripples and mitigation methods are considered [47]. Further improvements were reported recently, related to compensation algorithms based on machine learning and is now operational [51]. A Henon map approach is used for the particle tracking simulation, calculating the beam distribution on a turn-by-turn basis, which allows faster calculations for large parameter scans. In an earlier paper, the same Henon map approach was used to determine the frequency response of the beam on a wide parameter space [41]. Empty-bucket channelling and COSE are investigated for MedAustron [16,44]; design considerations were performed commonly between both institutes. Further on, RF place displacement is demonstrated at PS for burst extraction, e.g., required for oncology therapy known as FLASH method [52].

At GSI, tune scan extraction is frequently used for coasting beams, and for several years, micro-structure improvements have been worked out. In particular, a modulation of the tune, referred to as tune wobbling, has a significant impact and is now in routine operation [53]. The horizontal tune is modulated by injecting an additional current to a quadrupole with a value 10^{-4} level with respect to the main quadrupoles, which is about a factor 3 to 10 above the inherent power supply ripples; the frequency band is 3 to 10 kHz. It results in a periodic variation of the separatrix, which counteracts the sudden change of the separatrix by power supply ripples. The modulation results in a more uniform particle extraction than a sudden power supply ripple, reducing the 0.1 to 0.5 ms long breaks without beam extraction. Moreover, it causes a larger spread of the transit time and, hence, a smoothing of the extracted current fluctuations. The transit time is defined as the time between the separatrix crossing and the arrival at the electron static septum; typical values are between 100 and 1000 turns in the synchrotron. Investigations at GSI concerning the transit time simulations and

measurements are reported in [53,54,56]. Further on, the relation between the horizontal emittance and the micro-structure was investigated experimentally showing a positive influence for small emittances [55].

Generally, bunched beams have a better micro-structure than coasting beams due to a faster separatrix crossing and, for some parameters, a larger transit time spread. At most facilities, the bunching is generated by the accelerating cavity operated in the range of 1 to 10 MHz (with the exception of SPS, where higher acceleration frequencies are used). The time structure is imprinted on the extracted beam current, which is acceptable for medical facilities but not for fixed-target experiments at GSI and CERN. The extracted beam time structure at GSI comprises narrow peaks of 1 to 10 ns width [56-58], separated by the RF period of typically 200 ns; this break leads to the dead-time of the user's detectors. Bunching at higher frequencies would be an advantage; a cavity operated at 80 MHz was installed at GSI and tested with a beam using tune scan extraction [56,59]. Generally, the duty factor is improved. However, the micro-structure varies as a function of time during the extraction. It is caused by the crossing of synchro-betatron resonances related to the higher synchrotron tune with a scaling of $Q_{\text{syn}} \propto \sqrt{h \cdot U_{\text{rf}}}$ with h being the harmonic number (at the described experiment $h = 90$) and U_{rf} the cavity voltage [56,60]. The variation of the duty factor is more pronounced due to multiple crossings of resonances during the tune scan compared to bunching at lower frequencies, as confirmed by tracking simulations.

6 Dissemination of Results

The IFAST-REX funding strengthened the consortium members' collaboration and led to an intense discussion. One example is an online collaboration meeting with 40 participants at the start of the project; see <https://indico.gsi.de/event/11868/>. Further online and personal meetings were organised. In particular, PhD students and young scientists initialised dedicated online meetings to discuss and document their actual topics. The spill time structure improvement is a very active field which concerns all facilities with slow extraction. During the project's duration, many reports were published in conference proceedings and refereed journals; they are cited in the above text.

Consortium members executed several theses during the IFAST-REX funding period to improve the slow extraction time structure. The theses' authors and titles are in alphabetic order:

- Pablo A. Arrutia Sota, Advanced RF techniques for CERN's future slow-extracted beams, PhD Thesis Keble College, University of Oxford, 2024, see <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:36a58607-0a79-4dcd-9007-79a7f50e33d5>.
- Thomas Bass, A Comparative Analysis of Simulations and Experimental Outcomes: Slow Extraction Driven by RF Transverse Excitation at the CERN Proton Synchrotron, Master Thesis Royal Holloway, University of London, 2023, see <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2884477>.
- Florian Khteubl, Slow Extraction Optimization for the MedAustron Synchrotron, PhD Thesis Technical University Vienna, 2024, see <https://doi.org/10.34726/hss.2024.88260>.
- Philipp Niedermayer, Transverse excitation for beam diagnostics and slow extraction from synchrotrons, PhD Thesis Goethe University Frankfurt am Main, 2025, submitted.
- Rebecca Taylor, Slow Extraction: Upgrades for Next Ion Medical Machines at FLASH timescales, PhD Thesis Imperial College London, Physics Department, 2024, see <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2915795?ln=de>.
- Jiangyan Yang, Exploration of slow extraction beam quality and improvements at SIS18, PhD Thesis Goethe University Frankfurt am Main, 2025, submitted.

The developments performed within the consortium were presented in an international in-person workshop organised and sponsored by IFAST-REX partners in February 2024, see <https://indico.gsi.de/event/18184/>. It was the fifth workshop within a series, started in 2016 and will be continued in October 2025 at BNL, USA. The four days' workshop in Wiener Neustadt hosted 63 participants. Worldwide leading experts from Europe, USA, China and Japan discussed all relevant topics for slow extraction. The program comprised talks, posters, a guided tour at MedAustron, and extensive discussion sessions to summarize the actual achievements and enable collaborations. Improving the micro-structure is one major topic, and the status and further ideas are documented in the workshop's talks and dedicated discussion sessions.

7 Conclusion

As the result of IFAST-REX, a significant improvement of the spill micro-structure was achieved, and the functionality of the technical deliverables was demonstrated. The progress is based on extensive beam dynamics studies, including analytical treatments and detailed simulations. As related to the novel, high-performance code Xsuite, versatile parameter scans could be executed, resulting in an extended insight into the relevant accelerator physics. Within an iterative process, beam-based experiments commonly executed at several facilities confirm the simulation results and trigger further advanced investigations on the experimental and theoretical side. In particular, the relation between the excitation signal type and the micro-structure was verified for the knock-out extraction. An optimized, multi-band signal type was realized, and its applicability at several facilities (COSY, HIT, SIS18) was demonstrated. It can serve as the basis for applications at other facilities. Joint studies were executed by consortium members from different facilities as initialized by the EU-sponsored task IFAST-REX. The achievements were published in conference proceedings, in refereed journals, and as PhD theses.

Further on, detailed simulations and experiments were performed for the alternative extraction method by empty-bucket channelling. Within a shared effort between consortium members (mainly CERN and MedAustron), improvements were demonstrated for this method as well incorporating novel ideas. Both institutes collaborate on further topics which are important for slow extraction.

On the technical side, two novel instruments are now available. The first one is the very sensitive measurement of the AC current from the power supplies realized by the combination of two transformers reaching a record resolution of $\Delta I_{AC}/I_{DC} < 10^{-6}$ for a DC current $I_{DC} \leq 5$ kA and providing a bandwidth of 10 Hz to 40 kHz. Several design iterations were executed very competently by the company BergozTM to reach the demanding specifications; TRL 7 was reached. Detailed performance tests were executed at BergozTM and CERN with the participation of GSI scientists. The device is now available as a sensor for a feedback loop to stabilize the power supply current, which is the primary source of the beam's micro-structure fluctuations.

The second technical device is related to the knock-out extraction. The detailed specifications for the excitation signal are based on beam dynamics studies and experimental verifications as worked out during the project duration. On the technical side, a high-performance low-level control by either commercial software-defined radio hardware or in-house solutions was demonstrated as an appropriate solution. The GNU-Radio software for commercial hardware can realize the required multi-band excitation signal for an improved micro-structure. A contribution to the open GNU Radio project was required by one of the consortium members. Moreover, a macro-spill feedback can be included in this solution. Company Barthel HF-Technik realized a high-performance RF amplifier with 500 W output power on a wide bandwidth of 0.1 to 20 MHz required for the multi-band excitation. Moreover, the amplifier can be operated in a cw-mode for any load impedance. The amplifier could be applied at medical facilities, GSI for SIS18, the FAIR synchrotron SIS100 and possibly at CERN PS. Both technical solutions should now be investigated for applications by the consortium members. The required adaptations are expected to be realizable using the developed technologies as TRL 7 was reached.

8 References

- [1] P. Forck et al. (2000), Measurement and Improvements of the Time Structure of slowly extracted Beam from a Synchrotron, in Proc. EPAC'2000, Vienna, Austria, June 2000, pp. 2237-2239. <https://accelconf.web.cern.ch/e00/PAPERS/MOP4B03.pdf>
- [2] S. Sorge, P. Forck, and R. Singh (2018), Measurements and Simulations of the Spill Quality of slowly extracted Beams from the SIS-18 Synchrotron, in Proc. IPAC'18, Vancouver, BC, Canada, April 2018, pp. 924-926. <https://doi.org/doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2018-TUPAF081>
- [3] P.J. Niedermayer et al. (2023), Investigation of Micro Spill in RF KO Extraction using tailored Excitation Signals, in Proc. IPAC'23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 2427-2430. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-TUPM094>
- [3] D. Belohrad (2011), Beam Charge Measurements, in Proc. DIPAC 2011, Hamburg, Germany, May 2011, paper WEOC01, pp. 564-568, <https://jacow.org/DIPAC2011/papers/WEOC01.pdf>
- [4] P. Forck (2024), Beam Instrumentation, in Proceedings of the Joint Universities Accelerator School (JUAS): Courses and exercises, E. Métral (ed.), CERN Yellow Reports: School Proceedings CERN-2024-003, pp. 1339-1528. <https://doi.org/10.23730/CYRSP-2024-003>
- [5] ACCT Manual company Bergoz™, <https://www.bergoz.com/products/acct/>
- [6] T. Yamaguchi et al. (2020), Slow beam extraction from a synchrotron using a radio frequency knock-out system with a broadband colored noise signal, Nucl. Instrum. Meth. B 462, pp. 177–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2019.10.005>
- [7] K. Mizushima et al. (2011), Making beam spill less sensitive to power supply ripple in resonant slow extraction. Nucl. Instrum. Meth, A 638, pp. 19–23 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2011.02.056>
- [8] T. Nakanishi (2010), Dependence of a frequency bandwidth on a spill structure in the RF-knockout extraction. Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A 621, pp. 62–67 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2010.04.070>
- [9] K. Noda, et al. (2002), Advanced RF-KO slow-extraction method for the reduction of spill ripple. Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A 492, pp. 253–263 (2002). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002\(02\)01319-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002(02)01319-0)
- [10] K. Noda et al. (2002), Source of spill ripple in the RF-KO slow-extraction method with FM and AM, Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A 492, pp. 241–252 (2002). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002\(02\)01318-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002(02)01318-9)
- [11] P. A. Arrutia Sota et al. (2023), Benchmarking Simulations of Slow Extraction Driven by RF Transverse Excitation at the CERN Proton Synchrotron, in Proc. IPAC'23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 2487-2490. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-TUPM116>

- [12] E.P. Johnson et al. (2023), Beam delivery of high-energy ion beams for irradiation experiments at the CERN Proton Synchrotron, in Proc. IPAC'23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 315-318. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-MOPA115>
- [13] P. A. Arrutia Sota et al. (2025), Combining Quadrupole-Driven Slow Extraction with RFKO at the CERN SPS, in Proc. IPAC'25, Taipei, Taiwan, in preparation.
- [14] E. Feldmeier et al. (2022), Upgrade of the Slow Extraction System of the Heidelberg Ion-Beam Therapy Centre's Synchrotron, in Proc. IPAC'22, Bangkok, Thailand, June 2022, pp. 2509–2512. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-THPOST029>
- [15] P. J. Niedermayer and R. Singh (2022), Novel Beam Excitation System Based on Software-Defined Radio, in Proc. IBIC'22, Kraków, Poland, Sep. 2022, pp. 133-136. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2022-MOP36>
- [16] F. Kühleubl et al. (2023), Investigating Alternative Extraction Methods at MedAustron, in Proc. IPAC'23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp 2419-2422. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-TUPM091>
- [17] M. Wolf et al. (2023), Expansion of the μ TCA based direct sampling LLRF at MedAustron for hadron synchrotron applications, in Proc. IPAC'23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 4168-4170. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-THPA091>
- [18] GNU-Radio, <https://www.gnuradio.org>
- [19] P. J. Niedermayer and R. Singh (2022), Transverse Excitation and Applications for Beam Control, in Proc. IPAC'22, Bangkok, Thailand, June 2022, pp. 251-253. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-MOPOPT011>
- [20] E.C. Cortes Garcia et al. (2022), Optimisation of the spill quality for the hadron therapy at the Heidelberg Ion-Beam Therapy Centre, Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A, vol.1040, 167137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2022.167137>
- [21] E.C. Cortes Garcia et al. (2022), Horizontal Beam Response at Extraction Conditions at the Heidelberg Ion-beam Therapy Centre, in Proc. IPAC'22, Bangkok, Thailand, June 2022, pp 2096-2099. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEPOTK022>
- [22] P. J. Niedermayer et al. (2023), Investigation of micro spill in RF KO extraction using tailored excitation signals, in Proc. IPAC'23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 2427-2430. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-TUPM094>
- [23] P. J. Niedermayer and R. Singh (2024), Excitation signal optimization for minimizing fluctuations in knock out slow extraction, Scientific Reports, 14, 10310 (2024). <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-024-60966-y>
- [24] P. Niedermayer (2025), Transverse excitation for beam diagnostics and slow extraction from synchrotrons, PhD Thesis Goethe University Frankfurt am Main, 2025.

- [25] Y. Kobayashi (1970), Theory of the resonant beam ejection from synchrotrons, Nucl. Instrum. Methods 83, 77 (1970). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X\(70\)90537-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X(70)90537-9)
- [26] P. Niedermayer, R. Singh and E. Feldmeier (2025), Knock-out slow extraction using betatron sidebands at high harmonics, in preparation for Phys. Rev. Applied.
- [27] P. Niedermayer et al. (2024), First implementation of RF-KO slow extraction at COSY, in Proc. IPAC'24, Nashville, TE, USA, May 2024, pp 3568-3570. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2024-THPR34>
- [28] P. Niedermayer, R. Singh and R. Geißler (2023), Software-Defined Radio Based Feedback System for Beam Spill Control in Particle Accelerators, in Proc. 13th GNU Radio Conf., Tempe, AZ, USA, Sep. 2023. <https://pubs.gnuradio.org/index.php/grcon/article/view/133/119>
- [29] P. Niedermayer and R. Singh (2025), Spill optimization system for improving slow extraction at GSI, in Proc. IPAC'25, Taipei, Taiwan, May 2025, in preparation.
- [30] C. Schoemers et al. (2015), The intensity feedback system at Heidelberg Ion-Beam Therapy Centre, Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. A, vol. 795, pp. 92-99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2015.05.054>
- [31] E. C. Cortés García (2021), Investigation of RF-signals for the slow extraction at HIT's medical synchrotron. Master's thesis, TU Darmstadt, Germany, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.26083/tuprints-00020811>
- [32] T. Shiokawa et al. (2021), Slow beam extraction method from synchrotron for uniform spill and fast beam switching using an RF knock-out method of multi-band colored noise signal—POP Experiment and simulation, Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A, vol.1010 (2021), 165560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2021.165560>
- [33] E. Renner et al. (2024), Investigating pulsed slow extraction schemes at the MedAustron synchrotron, in Proc. IPAC'24, Nashville, TE, USA, May 2024, pp. 3595-3598. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2024-THPR41>
- [34] S. Savazzi et al. (2019), Implementation of RF-KO Extraction at CNAO, in Proc. IPAC'19, Melbourne, Australia, May 2019, pp3469-3471. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2019-THPMP010>
- [35] M. Pullia et al. (2016), 'Betatron Core driven slow Extraction at CNAO and MedAustron, in Proc. IPAC'16, Busan, Korea, May 2016, pp. 1330-1333. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2016-TUPMR037>
- [36] W. Höfle, Transverse Damper (2012), Proceedings of Chamonix 2012 workshop on LHC Performance. https://cds.cern.ch/record/1492958/files/WH_3_05.pdf
- [37] A. Oeftiger and R. Singh (2022), Diagnostics with Quadrupole Pick-Ups at SIS18, in Proc. IBIC'22, Kraków, Poland, Sep. 2022, pp. 186-191. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2022-TU1I2>

- [38] G. Iadarola et al. (2023), Xsuite: An integrated beam physics simulation framework, in Proc. HB'23, Geneva, Switzerland, Oct. 2023, pp 73-80.
<https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-HB2023-TUA2I1>
- [39] G. Iadarola et al. (2024), Xsuite: An integrated beam physics simulation framework, in Proc. IPAC'24, Nashville, TE, USA, May 2024, pp 2623-2626.
<https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2024-WEPR56>
- [40] M. Henon (1976), A two-dimensional mapping with a strange attractor, Commun. Math. Phys. 50, p 69. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/BF01608556>
- [41] M. Pari et al. (2021), Characterization of the slow extraction frequency response, Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams, 24, 083501 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.24.083501>
- [42] C.E. Cortes Garcia et al. (2024), Interpretation of the horizontal beam response near the third integer resonance, Phys. Rev Accel. Beams 27, 124001 (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.27.124001>
- [43] P. Niedermayer and R.Singh (2024), Excitation of nonlinear second order betatron sidebands for knock-out slow extraction at the third-integer resonance, Phys. Rev Accel. Beams 27, 082801 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.27.082801>
- [44] F. Kuhteubl (2024), Slow Extraction Optimization for the MedAustron Synchrotron, PhD Thesis Technical University Vienna, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.34726/hss.2024.88260>
- [45] R. Taylor (2024), Slow Extraction: Upgrades for Next Ion Medical Machines at FLASH timescales, PhD Thesis Imperial College London, Physics Department, 2024.
<https://cds.cern.ch/record/2915795?ln=de>
- [46] V. Kain et al. (2019), Resonant slow extraction with constant optic for improved Separatrix Control at the extraction septum, Phys. Rev Accel. Beams 22, 101001 (2019).
<https://doi.org/doi:10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.22.101001>
- [47] P. A. Arrutia Sota, F. Velotti, and, M. Fraser (2024), Effects of dipole power converter ripple during empty-bucket channelling, in Proc. IPAC'24, Nashville, TE, USA, May 2024, pp. 1790-1793. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2024-TUPC70>
- [48] P. A. Arrutia Sota et al. (2023), RF techniques for spill quality improvement in the SPS, in Proc. IPAC'23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 319-322.
<https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-TUPM116>
- [49] P. A. Arrutia Sota et al. (2024), Empty-bucket techniques for spill-quality improvement at the CERN Super Proton Synchrotron, Phys. Rev Accel. Beams 27, 074001 (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.27.074001>
- [50] P. A. Arrutia Sota (2024), Advanced RF techniques for CERN's future slow-extracted beams, PhD Thesis Keble College, University of Oxford, 2024.
<https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:36a58607-0a79-4dcd-9007-79a7f50e33d5>

- [51] V. Kain et al. (2024), Slow extracted spill ripple control in the CERN SPS using adaptive Bayesian optimisation, in Proc. IPAC'24, Nashville, TE, USA, May 2024, pp. 1790-1793. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2024-TUPS55>
- [52] P. A. Arrutia Sota et al. (2022), Millisecond burst extractions from synchrotrons using RF phase displacement acceleration, Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A 1039 (2022) 167007. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900222004363>
- [53] R. Singh, P. Forck, and S. Sorge (2020), Reducing Fluctuations in Slow-Extraction Beam Spill Using Transit-Time-Dependent Tune Modulation, Phys. Rev. Applied 13, 044076 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevApplied.13.044076>
- [54] J. Yang, P. Forck, R. Singh, and S. Sorge (2023), Study on Spill Quality and Transit Times for Slow Extraction from SIS18, in Proc. IPAC'23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 2435-2438. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-TUPM097>
- [55] J. Yang, et al. (2022), Improvement of Spill Quality for Slowly Extracted Ions at GSI-SIS18 via Transverse Emittance Exchange, in Proc. IPAC'22, Bangkok, Thailand, June 2022, pp. 2093-2095. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-WEPOTK021>
- [56] J. Yang (2025), Exploration of slow extraction beam quality and improvements at SIS18, PhD Thesis Goethe University Frankfurt am Main, 2025.
- [57] T. Milosic, P. Forck, and R. Singh (2021), Sub-ns Single-Particle Spill Characterization for Slow Extraction, in Proc. IBIC'21, Pohang, Korea (remote), Sep. 2021, pp. 438-442. <https://doi.org/doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2021-WEPP28>
- [58] J. Yang, et al. (2022), Beam Characterization of Slow Extraction Measurement at GSI-SIS18 for Transverse Emittance Exchange Experiments, in Proc. IBIC'22, Krakow, Poland, Sep. 2022, pp. 318-322. <https://doi.org/doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2022-TUP36>
- [59] K. Gross et al. (2024), Development of a spill-structure manipulation cavity and first experiment with beam in SIS18, in Proc. IPAC'24, Nashville, TE, USA, May 2024, pp. 1432-1435. <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2024-TUPR07>
- [60] S. Sorge, P. Forck, and R. Singh (2023), Spill ripple mitigation by bunched beam extraction with high frequency synchrotron motion, Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 26, 014402 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.26.014402>